

EVALUATION OF THE PERFORMANCE OF ROBOTIC WELDING CELLS BY MODELING WITH TIMED PETRI NETS. CASE STUDY

Author(s)*: Florin BLAGA¹, Alin POP², Vochita HULE³, Cristina MOCAN⁴, Cosmin POPA⁵

Position: Prof., PhD¹, Lecturer, PhD², Assoc. Prof., PhD³, Engineer⁴, Engineer⁵

University: University of Oradea

Address: Oradea, Universității Str., No. 1, Romania

Email: fblaga@uoradea.ro¹, alinpop23@yahoo.com², vhule@uoradea.ro³,
mocan.cristina94@yahoo.com⁴

Webpage: <https://www.uoradea.ro>

Abstract

Purpose – The subject is to develop a model with timed Petri nets of a robotic welding cell.

Methodology/approach - The information used in the construction of the model (s) with timed Petri nets were: the sequence of sequences specific to the welding process within the robotic cell; duration of sequences; number and type of parts that are assembled by welding; cell layout. With this information, three model variants with timed Petri nets were built

Findings – The paper presents how generalized timed Petri nets can be used to model and simulate robotic welding cells.

The modeling and simulation process is an iterative process several varieties of models with generalized timed Petri nets have been developed.

Research limitations/implications – The subject is to develop a model with timed Petri nets of a robotic welding cell. Using this model, by simulation, the performance of the cell will be evaluated and the problems that appear in the manufacturing process will be highlighted

Practical implications Using the model, by simulation, the performance of the cell will be evaluated and the problems that appear in the manufacturing process will be highlighted.

Originality/value – Models with generalized timed Petri nets, the final version, have several attributes: takes into account the actual welding sequences within the cell; also models the supply processes with parts; integrates the cell within a manufacturing line.

Key words: Modeling, simulation, Petri nets, robotic cell.

Introduction

Welding is a very common technological process used in the automotive industry, especially in assembling car bodies. Modern assembly lines are characterized by the fact that they have complex devices in their component and in most cases are robotic.

Car bodies are complex assemblies which, in turn, are obtained using subassemblies such as: lower floor, side faces, front assembly, engine compartment, doors and bonnets. These subassemblies are obtained, several times, by joining by welding some pieces of deep drawing and bent sheet (Figure 1).

In the process of welding the sheets, spot welding without filler material or continuous welding with filler material is used by the process with fusible electrode in protective inert gas (MIG) medium. Regardless of the welding method chosen, it is preferable that the assembly of the body elements be done mechanized or automated with the help of industrial robots (Figure 2). The use of industrial robots leads to: increasing productivity and quality, reducing energy costs, material costs and labor.

Figure 1. Car body assembly

Figure 2. Industrial welding robot

These robots are equipped with weld guns. The mobile welding pliers are manipulated together with their actuator by the robot. These can be of 3 types:

Type C - performs a translational movement, its actuating cylinder being connected directly to the moving electrode (Figure 3);

Type X - are the most common, they perform a rotational movement (Figure 4);

Type D - performs a translational movement and is used for vertical welding (Figure 5).

Figure 3. Type C Welding gun

Figure 4. Type X Welding gun

Figure 5. Type D Welding gun

Figure 6. Welding cell

A robotic welding cell may contain a geometric station in which the assembly is done through the welding points and, as the case may be, a respot station in which the assembly will be done through those

welding points that could not be done in the geometry station. Figure 6 shows the scheme of the working process in such a cell. In the geometric station, the body elements are first positioned in the devices and then fixed with pneumatic clamps to hold the parts in place. The next step is welding at the geometry points after which the assembly is released by the clamps. After that, the subassembly can be managed by a clamping device which is taken from the geometric station and holds it until the respite phase lasts. In the respot station, the remaining welding points, also called respot points, will also be welded. The welding procedure is described in figure 6.

Description of the subassembly to be welded and of the welding station

The welding cell is intended for assembling the structure *Central lower floor subassembly*. This subassembly has three components: sheet 1, welded subassembly and sheet 2 (Figure 7)

Figure 7. Central lower floor subassembly components

The automated welding cell is of human-robot type and works sequentially, ie first, the operator loads the sheet elements to be welded after which the robot performs the welding operation. The body elements to be assembled are oriented by means of the pins and fixed with the help of pneumatic clamps in the geometric welding station. Figure 8 shows the components to be welded positioned and fixed in the welding station. Welding is performed with the help of welding pliers. All welding points defined on the road elements can be accessed by the welding pliers, so there will be no need for respot points. Welding a point takes 4 sec. Welding is done successively, only one welding point at each step until all welding points are executed. The robot starts spot welding with type X guns, and then with type C guns (Figure 9). Figure 10 shows the station and the numbering of the component units. A complete cell operating cycle is composed of a sequence of sequences. These sequences and their durations are presented in Table 1.

Figure 8. The components to be welded are positioned and fixed

Figure 9. Type C gun welding

Figure 10. The units within the station

Table 1. Process sequences

No	Description	Operator/ Robot/ No. Unit	Quantity	Operation time
Loading of the sheets by the operator / approximately 65-70 sec				
1	Manual sheet loading 1		1	10.5
2	Manual loading of the blank	With the help of a handling device	1	39
3	Manual sheet loading 2		1	19
Welding station				
4	Closing the pneumatic clamps	Unit 02,03	1	3
5	Closing the pneumatic clamps	Unit 04.,05,06,07,08, 10,12,13	1	1.5
6	The robot turns 90 °	Towards the geometric station	1	1.7
7	Spot welding with the robot	Welding with X-type welding pliers	12	48
8	The robot turns 180 °		1	2.7
9	Changing the pliers (the pliers are on the support)	Lifting type C welding pliers	1	15
10	The robot turns 180 °		1	2.7
11	Spot welding with the robot	Welding with type C welding pliers	10	40
12	Opening the pneumatic clamps	Unit 02,03	1	3
13	Opening the pneumatic clamps	Unit 04.,05,06,07,08, 10,12,13	1	1
14	Pine cylinders retract	Unit 14,15,16	1	2
15	The robot turns 180 °		1	2.7
16	Changing the pliers (the pliers are on the support)	Lifting the gripper with the robot	1	15
17	The robot turns 180 °		1	2.7
18	The robot unloads the large blank	From the GEO station	1	8
19	Pine cylinders rise	Unit 14, 15, 16	1	2

Evaluation of welding cell performance by modeling and simulation with timed Petri nets

To evaluate the performance of the welding cell and to identify possible blockages, a model with Petri nets was developed. The models were made in the Visual Object Net ++ program. The activities performed by the human operator (loading the sheet 1, the welded semi-finished product and the sheet 2) are modeled by transitions to which timings have been associated, equal to the real times in which the human operator performs the respective actions. Also, the closing / opening sequences of the pneumatic clamps, the retraction and lifting of the pin cylinders were modeled with transitions. In the process that takes place in the welding cell, the robots perform complex sequences, such as: positioning (turning), performing welding points, changing the welding pliers, replacing the welding pliers with the gripper, evacuating the lower lower floor subassembly. All these sequences were modeled with timed transitions. Execution of a transition (realization of a real sequence) is possible if some conditions are met. These conditions are modeled in the Petri net through the positions. The transitions and positions of the three model variants are presented in table 2

Table 2. Petri net positions and transitions

No.	Symbol	Type	Description	Characteristics		
				Version 1	Version 2	Version 3
1	P1	Position	The operator is free	$m_0(P1)=1$	$m_0(P1)=1$	$m_0(P1)=1$
2	P2	Position	Stock of type 1 sheets	$m_0(P2)=150$	$m_0(P2)=160$	$m_0(P2)=20$
3	T1	Transition	Loading the sheet 1	$d_1=10,5$ sec	$d_1=10,5$ sec	$d_1=10,5$ sec
4	P3	Position	Table 1 is on the station	$m_0(P4)=0$	$m_0(P4)=0$	$m_0(P4)=0$
...
19	P11	Position	The robot is in position	$m_0(P11)=0$	$m_0(P11)=0$	$m_0(P11)=0$
20	T7	Transition	Welding the 12 (8) points with X-type welding pliers	$d_7=48$ sec	$d_7=32$ sec	$d_7=32$ sec
21	P12	Position	All 8 points are welded	$m_0(P12)=0$	$m_0(P12)=0$	$m_0(P12)=0$
22	T8	Transition	The robot rotates 180 °	$d_8=2,7$ sec	$d_8=2,7$ sec	$d_8=2,7$ sec
23	P13	Position	The robot is in position	$m_0(P13)=0$	$m_0(P13)=0$	$m_0(P13)=0$
24	T9	Transition	Replacing the welding pliers X with the tee type C	$d_9=15$ sec	$d_9=15$ sec	$d_9=15$ sec
25	P14	Position	Type C welding pliers are on the robot	$m_0(P14)=0$	$m_0(P14)=0$	$m_0(P14)=0$
26	T10	Transition	The robot rotates 180 °	$d_{10}=2,7$ sec	$d_{10}=2,7$ sec	$d_{10}=2,7$ sec
27	P15	Position	The robot is in position	$m_0(P15)=0$	$m_0(P15)=0$	$m_0(P15)=0$
28	T11	Transition	Welding the 10 (6) points with type C welding pliers	$d_{11} 40$ sec	$d_{11}=24$ sec	$d_{11}=24$ sec
...
44	T19	Transition	The pin cylinders rise	$T_{19}=2$ sec	$T_{19}=2$ sec	$T=2$ sec
45	P25	Position	The pin cylinders are raised	$m_0(P25)=0$	$m_0(P25)=0$	$m_0(P25)=0$
46	P26	Position	Consumption table 1	-	-	$m_0(P26)=0$
47	T20	Transition	Supply of sheet metal stock 1	-	-	-
48	P27	Position	Sheet stock reload number counter 1	-	-	$m_0(P27)=0$
49	P28	Position	Blank consumption counter	-	-	$m_0(P28)=0$
50	T21	Transition	Supply of blank stock	-	-	-
51	P29	Position	Counter number of reloads of the blanks stock	-	-	$m_0(P29)=0$
52	P30	Position	Consumption counter table 2	-	-	$m_0(P30)=0$
53	T22	Transition	Supply of sheet metal stock 2	-	-	-
54	P31	Position	Sheet stock reload number 2	-	-	$m_0(P31)=0$
55	P32	Position	Confirmation of completion of sheet metal assembly	-	-	$m_0(P32)=0$
56	T23	Transition	The waiting time of the station until the operator is free	-	-	-

In the first model version (Figure 11) it was considered that welding with pliers type X is done in 12 points and lasts 48 seconds (transition T7 has timing 48). It is also welded in 10 points with type C pliers. This sequence lasts 40 seconds (transition T11 has a timing of 40). Using the model with Petri nets, the simulation of the cell functioning during an 8-hour work shift was performed. The simulation result indicates that 133 *Central lower floor subassemblies* can be obtained.

Figure 11. Model with timed Petri nets. Version 1

Analyzing, together with the beneficiary (client) the results of the simulation and, at the proposal of the designer, it was decided to reduce the number of welding points from 22 to 14. Thus, with type X pliers the welding will be done in 8 points. The duration of this sequence is 32 seconds. With type C pliers, 6 points will be welded in 24 seconds. With these data, variant 2 of the model with timed Petri nets was built, the variant in which transition T7 has timing 32 and transition T11 has timing 24. Simulation of cell operation, in version 2 of the model, highlighted the possibility of achieving 157 of *Central lower floor subassemblies*.

In version 3 of the model (Figure 12) other aspects of the cell operation are taken into account, so that the model is as close as possible to the real system. Thus, it is considered that the storage space of the sheets, respectively of the subassemblies, which are welded, is not enough to store the necessary for 8 hours. Consequently, the stocks, modeled with positions P2 (Table 1), P4 (welded semi-finished product) and P6 (Table 2), will be replenished periodically during the 8 hours. Items P26, P28 and P30 count the number of Tables 1, Welded Subassemblies, Tables 2 consumed from stock. When the number of tokens in these positions (the number of components used) is equal to the capacity of the stocks, their replenishment is done. Stock replenishment is modeled, through transitions T20, T21 and

T22. The transition T20 is executable when in position P26 there are 20 tokens, the arc $P26 \rightarrow T20$ has the load 20 (in the real system 20 pieces of sheet 1 were used). Transition T21 is executable when in position P28 there are 2 tokens, arc $P28 \rightarrow T21$ has load 2 (in the real system 2 pieces of welded subassembly were used). Transition T22 is executable when in position P30 there are 20 tokens, arc $P20 \rightarrow T22$ has a load of 20 (in the real system 2 pieces of sheet 2 were used). Given that arches appear in the model whose loads are greater than 1, the model is a generalized timed Petri net. Positions P27, P29 and P31 count stock replenishment cycles.

Figure 12. Model with timed Petri nets. Variant 3

After simulating the operation of the cell for 8 hours, the number of replenish sequences for each of the three stocks can be highlighted. Thus, the stocks for Sheet 1 and Table 2 landmarks were replenished 7 times (in positions P26 and P31 there are 7 tokens each - Figure 12). Replenish moments can be highlighted by the graphs associated with the positions. Figure 11 shows the graph associated with

position 31. Also, the 79 tokens in position P29 indicate that the stock corresponding to the *Welded subassembly* must be replenished 79 times during an exchange.

Conclusions

The paper presented how using modeling with timed Petri nets can evaluate the performance of a welding cell served by a human operator and a robot. The models were gradually developed. Thus, in the first variant the number of welding points was 22, having a cell cycle duration of 215 sec, and after simulating the operation of the station for 8 hours, it was found that 133 pieces were welded to the lower central floor subassemblies. The number of welding points was reduced from 22 to 14, and the cycle time decreased to 183 sec, ie by 32 sec. After simulating the operation of the 8h station, it was found that 157 pieces of *Central lower floor subassemblies* were welded.

Version 3 included in the model with timed Petri nets and stock refueling sequences with components that are welded. The model becoming a generalized timed Petri net.

Therefore, modeling and simulation with Petri nets provides important information about the dynamic behavior of the modeled system. Modeling and simulation also offer the possibility to evaluate the performance of the modeled system and to suggest improvements or changes.

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